

The challenges facing the healthcare system in Somalia: A review and The Way Forward

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Abstract:

Background: The civil war devastated the state of Somalia's infrastructure, especially its health system. The health sector faces rebuilding challenges due to a lack of qualified personnel, enough funding, and efficient governance. Furthermore, post-war decentralization, deregulation, and general privatization of the service sector have significantly altered the healthcare landscape. **Methods:** In this review article, we provide a *comprehensive review* to address the challenges facing Somali healthcare, using published studies from the following databases: Pubmed, Google Scholar, Global Health, Popline, Medline, Embase, and Scopus. **Conclusion:** The work to improve health in Somalia continues, with diseases like non-communicable and communicable posing significant challenges. The lack of research institutes and human resources hinders the effective implementation of health policies.

Keywords: Healthcare Challenges, Public Health Services, Humanitarian aid, internally displaced people, Covid-19 Pandemic.

Introduction

Somalia's healthcare system is among the world's worst, with government health spending accounting for 1% of total spending. Insufficient taxation and a lack of strategic knowledge hinder the effective financing of healthcare demands. Somalia requires increased medical and nursing staff to meet diverse needs, while the health sector's financial needs remain high due to low health indicators and high operational costs [1]. Somalia faces severe health challenges due to its long-standing civil conflict, persistent food shortages, and malnutrition. The country's health system is severely impacted, with 2.6 million people fleeing their homes. The lack of humanitarian aid and high food prices, compounded by ongoing conflict, insecurity, and disease outbreaks, pose a significant threat to public health and child development. In

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countries affected by conflict and crisis, especially those experiencing protracted crises such as Somalia, the functioning of health systems is significantly compromised. Often, the situation gets so bad that public health care is no longer widely accessible [2]. The strengths and weaknesses of the strategies will be analyzed and used to identify possible gaps in the literature and draw lessons that can be applied to rebuilding, reforming, and strengthening the healthcare system in Somalia. There is a growing body of literature on how to build effective and sustainable health systems in Somalia, which will be reviewed in this review article [3].

Methodology

The theoretical framework of this review article was based on the World Health Organization's (WHO) building an effective health system For Somalia [4]. The impact of the conflict on the health status of the population and the health system, as well as pre-existing shortcomings, were explored to better understand the challenges faced in recovery. health system recovery. the World Health Organization's health systems framework highlights several important factors when rebuilding health systems in post-conflict contexts [5]. this review focuses on the *challenges* facing the *healthcare* system in Somalia.

Search Strategy

Published literature related to the health systems in Somalia. The search strategy included using various databases such as Global Health, PubMed, Popline, Medline, Scopus, EMBASE, and Google Scholar. Advanced database search tools “and” and “or” are used to cover all combinations and permutations of potential titles that can be searched. Figure 1 below shows a list of terms and their combinations used to find documents.

List of terms and combinations used for literature search

Figure 1. List of terms and combinations used for literature search.

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

The selected database yielded 108 results, of which 40 were removed due to duplicates. The titles of the remaining documents are then reviewed and removed from the search results if no keywords appear in the title or if it is deemed inappropriate for review. When searching for the Healthcare system in Somalia, references to existing articles were used to expand sources, and more specific searches were used.

Ensuring equitable access to medical products, vaccines, and technologies (MVT)

There is little literature on drugs, vaccines, and technology in the context of rebuilding health systems. Huff-Rousselle's unique research focuses on creating pharmaceutical and medical delivery systems. They found that funding often exceeds the absorptive capacity of the healthcare delivery system, leading to pressure to spend money on pilot projects and testing initiatives. often not sustainable. It is recommended that strategies for developing healthcare delivery systems in facilities should be simple [6].

Creating a mechanism to coordinate healthcare.

Somalia is among the countries where the GAP has made the greatest progress and its added value has been substantiated per the WHO Global Action Plan (GAP). The initial focus has been on strengthening primary healthcare and securing sustainable funding for healthcare. Somalia is susceptible to emergencies caused by natural disasters and disease outbreaks and is currently dealing with COVID-19. GAP agencies are investigating possibilities to assist in the finalization and execution of parts of a National Action Plan for Health Security. Healthcare standards in Somalia are being criticized by UN experts as being dangerously low. The UN expert called on the international community to guarantee the provision of basic social services, such as drinking water, sanitation facilities, housing, and health care education for all children, particularly girls. they recommended that the Government expand its delivery of public health services, taking into consideration the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, and increase funding for its health system. Somalia's response to COVID-19 and future health threats involves ensuring that everyone has access to health. The first COVID-19 case in Somalia was declared on March 16, 2020, as per the World Health Organization (WHO). The government has been making determined efforts to strengthen its health system, move towards universal health coverage (UHC), and strengthen preparedness through the development of a National Action Plan for Health Security [7] Fig 2.

Figure 2. De Martini Covid-19 isolation Center in Benadir, Somalia supported by WHO.

Burden of disease

Due to epidemiological and demographic changes, Somalia still must deal with a dual burden of noncommunicable diseases and maternal, newborn, and nutritional disorders as well as communicable infections. In 2019, the Global Burden of Disease 2019 revealed that communicable diseases, such as tuberculosis, lower respiratory infections, and diarrhoeal diseases, were the leading causes of death and disability in Somalia. Although mortality from communicable diseases decreased between 2000 and 2019, noncommunicable diseases increased. In 2019, communicable diseases and maternal, neonatal, and nutritional disorders accounted for 47% of all deaths, while noncommunicable diseases contributed to 45.6%. Injuries caused 7.35% of all deaths in 2019. Road injuries were among the top 10 leading causes of disability in 2019 [8].

■ Communicable, maternal, neonatal and nutritional diseases
■ Noncommunicable diseases
■ Injuries

Figure 3. Top 10 causes of death and disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) (per 100 000 population), age-standardized and both sexes, Somalia, 2019 <http://www.healthdata.org/gbd/2019>

Social determinants of health

Somali health status is influenced by factors such as education, income levels, migration status, and gender. Health disparities exist across geographic areas and socioeconomic groups, with factors like unsafe water, sanitation, air pollution, high blood pressure, and malnutrition posing risks. Education and wealth also influence health-seeking behavior and use of health services, with educated and wealthier

women more likely to use these services. The Global Burden of Disease Study 2019 identified unsafe water and sanitation, air pollution, high blood pressure, and malnutrition as leading risk factors for death and disability. From 2000 to 2019, unsafe water, sanitation, and malnutrition contributed less. (Source: Global Burden of Disease)

Funding of the Healthcare Sector

The health sector receives most of its funding from international donors, which is classified as off-budget. It is channeled directly to healthcare providers through a network of projects and instruments instead of through government systems and budgets. Although bypassing Somali systems is unsustainable and diminishes government accountability over the longer term, this has been a pragmatic response to poor levels of donor confidence in weak government financial systems. Witter also examined health financing in states that have experienced post-conflict and fragile situations. According to her, most studies had focused exclusively on the role of donors, citing the influence and funding they provided during the post-conflict period. Her assessment stated that developing government capacity and stewardship is becoming more important as states transition out of the post-conflict era. Witter pointed out that there is not enough literature on the long-term impact of post-conflict financial strategies on the health sector [9].

The impact of conflict on people's health status

Armed conflicts can have direct and indirect impacts on populations. Direct effects of war are those that have an immediate effect on the current health status of the population - including mortality, illness, stress, and the destruction of medical facilities. People face violence and torture, leading to long-term mental health problems as well as post-traumatic stress. Damage to medical facilities and looting reduce the ability to care for people in need. Data from conflict-affected countries shows that health facilities are often severely affected, leading to the destruction of medicines and equipment, drug shortages, and skyrocketing prices [10]. After the conflict, access to vital medicines for millions of people became a problem. As a result, people cannot access basic treatments and medicines for chronic diseases such as cardiovascular disease, hypertension, and diabetes as well as medicines to treat recurrent disease outbreaks such as the epidemic cholera and dengue fever, leading to high morbidity and mortality [11]. Negative impacts on public health initiatives such as vaccination programs could put people at greater risk of disease, with a greater impact on infants and mothers [12].

Somalia's health challenges

According to WHO, Somalia whose population is 15.4 million, is a country with a low income. The population is confronted with communicable diseases and respiratory infections, as well as issues related to maternal and child health-related morbidities and nutrition. The average lifespan is 55.7 years, and only 25% of Somali individuals have access to crucial healthcare services. The International Health Regulations Index

indicates that only 6% of the population in Somalia is safeguarded against health emergencies and infectious hazards.

Insecurity

Insecurity is a major issue in the Somali health system, particularly in southern and central Somalia. Political unpredictability leads to high turnover rates, hindering long-term growth and attracting qualified healthcare professionals [13].

Integrated Community Case Management(iCCM) program

Diarrhea, pneumonia, and malaria are still responsible for morbidity and mortality among children under five in Southwest Somalia. Tuboy, along with other nearby villages in Hudur district, does not have access to a health facility. With support from USAID through BRCiS, Action Against Hunger has started implementing the Integrated Community Case Management (ICCM) program in twelve villages to reduce morbidity and mortality rates caused by Diarrhea, pneumonia, and Malaria [14].

Discussion

Since 1990, the life expectancy in Somalia has gone up. Nevertheless, sustained mortality levels caused by communicable diseases and child and maternal mortality have possibly caused life expectancy to remain below the sub-Saharan average in 2020 (63.9 years for females and 60.3 for males) Table 2 [15]. Humanitarian actors have provided essential services to address the gaps in Somalia's health care system. HIV/AIDS has been reduced by the UNDP since 2004 through the creation of knowledge and awareness programs, increased testing, and advocacy for HIV/AIDS legislation. Managed by UNICEF, WHO, and the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), Somalia's Joint Health and Nutrition Programme (JHNP) has supported the institutional development of the Somali healthcare system and provided the Essential Package of Health Services (EPHS) [16]. Community health workers play a crucial work in delivering services in such remote villages where many can't access [17]. The current health system is essentially privatized, and it is restricted to major cities, leaving the poorest population in rural areas without affordable health care. Moreover, the national health system is fragmented, and the absence of unified health system governance has affected the capacity of national authorities to regulate the private sector and to partner with NGOs to deliver services to remote areas [18].

Macrae et al. studied the recovery of health services in post-conflict Uganda. The Ugandan government decided to restore pre-conflict health services and undertake a massive expansion of primary health care in underserved areas [19]. They chose this approach to avoid having to reform the financing and delivery of secondary and tertiary care. The challenges faced are that due to the prioritization of vertical health programs, capacity building is limited. Like in Somalia today, there were also many projects instead of a centralized national strategic policy. The increase in health

services provided also increases recurrent costs, which are often unsustainable, leading to high levels of donor dependency [20].

Figure 4. Shows the life expectancy in years. GBD-1990-2030

Study Limitation

This study's limitations are due to the severe limitations and gaps in data availability in Somalia and the lack of access to individual-level health data. This issue is crucial in describing and evaluating improvements in Healthcare. Reliable data sources were used to analyze national-level estimates produced by international agencies. By analyzing these data, we were able to produce trends for various key health indicators to evaluate Somalia's health development over the past three decades [21].

Lessons for Somalia

- The health system requires central pharmacies to be fully equipped with good, reliable distribution systems.
- Human resource development efforts must consider issues such as legal and regulatory frameworks, coordination, and oversight.
- The government must put in place coordination mechanisms right from the start of the recovery phase to avoid fragmentation and fragmentation of the health system.
- Management agencies must be responsible for monitoring, evaluating, and regulating the health system.
- Funding may be pooled to provide an amount that can be authorized by the Ministry of Health to achieve national health goals.
- Equitable infrastructure is needed to deploy a nationwide health information system.
- Health information needs to be centralized and managed in one seamless system, avoiding incompatible systems managed by different sponsors.
- Services must be provided by fully trained staff with a wide range of skills.

Casharada laga-barankaro Waxa ka mida (Somali Translation)

- Nidaamka caafimaadku wuxuu u baahan yahay farmasiyada dhexe in ay si buuxda isku qalabeeyaan oo ay yeshan hab-qaybin la isku halayn karo.
- Dadaalka horumarinta ilaha aadanaha waa in ay tixgeliyaan arrimaha ay ka mid yihiin qaab-dhismeedka sharci iyo sharci, isku-duwidda, iyo kormeerka.
- Dawladdu waa inay dejisaa habab isku-dubbarid laga bilaabo bilawga marxaladda soo kabashada si looga fogaado tafaraaruqa iyo kala-goynta nidaamka caafimaadka.
- Hay'adaha maarayntu waa inay masuul ka yihiin la socodka, qiimaynta, iyo nidaaminta nidaamka caafimaadka.
- Maalgelinta waxaa la mideyn karaa si loo bixiyo qaddar ay u oggolaan karto Wasaaradda Caafimaadka si loo gaaro yoolalka caafimaadka qaranka.
- Kaabayaal loo siman yahay ayaa loo baahan yahay si loo hawlgeliyo nidaamka macluumaadka caafimaadka dalka oo dhan.
- Macluumaadka caafimaadku waxa uu u baahan yahay in la meel mariyo oo lagu maamulo hal nidaam oo aan toos ahayn, iyada oo laga fogaanayo nidaamyada aan ku habboonayn ee ay maamulaan kafaala-qaadayaasha kala duwan.

Recommendations

- The focus is on enhancing the capabilities of healthcare professionals to deliver healthcare services and securing stable funding for healthcare financing.
- Further research is recommended on the country's healthcare systems.
- Future studies should aim to expand the range of perspectives by introducing as many different sources as possible.

Talooyin (Somali Translation)

- Diiradu waa kor u qaadida awooda xirfadlayaasha daryeelka caafimaadka si ay u bixiyaan adeegyada daryeelka caafimaadka iyo in la helo maalgelin xasiloon oo maalgelinta daryeelka caafimaadka.
- Cilmi baaris dheeraad ah ayaa lagula talinayaa hababka daryeelka caafimaadka ee dalka.
- Daraasadaha mustaqbalka waa in ay higsadaan si ay u ballaariyaan aragtiyaha kala duwan iyada oo la soo bandhigayo ilo kala duwan intii suurtagal ah

Conclusion

The health transition process in Somalia is still a work in progress. Non-communicable diseases' contribution to mortality and disability will continue to increase. Communicable, maternal, neonatal, and nutritional diseases continue to be a major health concern. Implementing evidence-based health interventions and improving the caliber of health policy and practices that follow are hampered by a lack of research institutes and human resources. Civil war devastated the state of Somalia's infrastructure, especially its health system.

Abbreviations

- Internally displaced people (IDP)
- Joint Health and Nutrition Programme (JHNP)

- Integrated Community Case Management (ICCM)
- World Health Organization (WHO)
- Essential Package of Health Services (EPHS).
- United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA).
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)
- Multiple Indicator Cluster Surveys (MICS)
- *Building Resilient Communities in Somalia (BRICS)*
- Global Burden Diseases (GBD)
- Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs)

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Authors Contribution: Dr. Sakarie Mustafe Hidig carried out the analyses, and study design and wrote the main manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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